

Corporate citizenship and organizational citizenship behavior: does Covid-19 affect the relationship?

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This research examines how COVID-19 has affected workers' behavior. Implementing Corporate Citizenship (CC) model, this study aimed to investigate the impact of COVID-19 Anxiety (CA) and COVID-19 Concern (COC) (acting as mediator) on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) and the influence of OCB on CC. Using the PLS-SEM model, we examined businesses in Colombia. Findings show CA has a positive direct impact on COC but a negative direct effect on OCB. Additionally, when COC serves as a mediator, CA positively affects CC. This research provides critical information to managers and practitioners about eliminating COVID-19's psychological effects on employees, particularly those in emerging markets and developing countries. When employees' anxiety levels increase, they get affected psychologically, and productivity is harmed. Also, when workers see their companies as good corporate citizens, they become good organizational citizens. Additional factors, like company size, cultural context, and countries comparisons, may be included in future studies.

Keywords: Corporate Citizenship, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, COVID-19

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Introduction

The Businesses are mobilizing to reclaim public trust, manage various risks, and meet growing stakeholder expectations while maintaining profitability and competitiveness in a globalized environment. Consequently, Corporate Citizenship (CC) has received increased attention recently. The concept of CC has evolved and provided a significant evaluation of the relationship between corporations and society (Maignan & Ferrell 2000). CC is expanding beyond legal compliance, public relations, and charity, leading organizations to become a fundamental aspect of corporate governance, strategy, risk management, and reputation building. Nevertheless, few studies have examined strategic approaches in international business, focusing on emerging and developing countries where poverty, environmental issues, and institutional deregulation make a case for the need to conduct CC activities.

Covid-19 has brought issues linked to CC to businesses and organizations. The pandemic has put good and bad companies' behaviors and ethical commitments to the test, especially those related to CC. During this crisis, many businesses have not only avoided unethical business practices. Still, they have also taken a proactive role in different CC initiatives to provide immediate aid and support to the population. The current epidemic presents various significant possibilities for those that take a more thoughtful and wise approach to CC.

Given the context and crisis created by the pandemic, it is crucial to study social perceptions of this *new normality*, which has resulted in the closure of countries, developed a global paralysis, deactivated all economies, and imposed an intense lockdown and social isolation to protect the population. This scenario has also increased the population's awareness of their personal and social responsibilities. According to Lee (2020), most businesses perceive a decline in economic activity caused by the COVID-19 crisis, while smaller firms face financial and liquidity issues. Another critical feature is how teleworking, cost modification, and tax debt deferral are integrated into a strategy for continuing operations. All the variables integrated into this scenario affect employees' performance, citizenship behavior, and how society perceives companies' CC behavior. A firm with a real CC commitment reinforces the existing bond among all stakeholders. Covid-19 could offer a substantial opportunity for businesses to participate actively in CC; however, the epidemic has driven numerous companies out of business or to the brink of failure. The pandemic has aggravated various long-standing socio-economic challenges, such as poverty and inequality.

Concerning the impact on economic development, it is ascertained that people's confinement results in decreased demand for goods and services; industries that have been significantly affected are tourism, entertainment, sports, retail, and restaurants. Two significant outcomes affected the labor market; first, teleworking facilitated activities from home; second, the vulnerable sectors were excluded due to a lack of resources and internet connection. The workplace has been impacted with equivalent strength.

OCB, defined as employee discretionary behavior, contributes to the understanding of effectiveness in organizations; hence, it is evolving as vital for businesses' long-term viability (Ndoja & Malekar 2020). CC is gaining attention as companies disregard the socio-legal and environmental implications of unethical behavior in favor of economic performance. Therefore, all stakeholders will see businesses that implement sustainable CC programs positively. Several studies have evaluated the influence of CC on employees as stakeholders (Evans & Davis 2014, Mathew & Krishnatray 2011). However, few have assessed the relationship between COVID-19, OCB, and CC. A company's good citizenship practices promote OCB among its employees (Jain & Rizvi 2020).

Swaen & Maignan (2003) found that citizenship was examined from an organizational and corporate viewpoint in the marketing and management literature, using the concepts of OCB and CC, respectively. While OCB is concerned with workers' attempts to behave ethically in their workplace, CC identifies companies' activities to promote good citizenship in society (p. 3). We aim to discuss the relationship between COVID-19, OCB and CC.

Literature Review

COVID-19 Anxiety

The coronavirus caused an economic slowdown and a rise in unemployment. Employees face social, economic, health, and psychological pressures that affect their mental stability and work attitudes. Most studies have focused on medical and nursing personnel (Kalaitzaki et al. 2020). Nevertheless, people's attitudes toward returning to work, particularly their work attitudes and OCB, are not well understood. Investigating work attitudes during the COVID-19 epidemic is critical; work attitudes influence work and organizational behaviors, job performance, and organizational effectiveness (Wang 2008).

There seems to be a lack of literature addressing factors influencing employees' psychological impact and attitudes in the workplace during the pandemic. Therefore, it is critical to understand the extent and

factors underlying employees' work attitudes to identify the need for assistance programs to prevent mental disorders and promote positive work attitudes. The current business scenario constrains people's interaction, personally and socially, by restricting physical contact and business operations, resulting in negative emotional impacts because of isolation and persistent fear of contagion. Among the most prevalent changes are stress, depression, anxiety, sleeplessness, and dietary changes, which will have a medium and long-term effect, eroding the individuals' mental health, especially in the labor force.

H1. CA is positively related to COC.

Some studies have reported health issues during the COVID-19 pandemic, including depression, anxiety, insomnia, appetite, and others (Lai et al. 2020, Zhang et al. 2020). Also, job insecurity is another significant concern for the global employee population. All those elements affect employee attitudes negatively and impact the organizational environment and employees' behavior. Therefore, combined job insecurity and health issues impact job satisfaction and OCB (Keim et al. 2014).

According to Mahmoud et al. (2021), due to stress and uncertainty, employees reduce discretionary contributions in order to preserve resources rejecting or not engaging in activities they are not obligated to do, such as cooperation among co-workers, improving job performance, and being able and open to participate in training to improve their skills.

H2. CA is positively related to OCB.

Confidence Crisis Management (CCM)

Job satisfaction is a term that refers to people's emotional emotions about their employment. The concept is essential since it pertains to employees' well-being (Gebauer & Lowman 2009). Theoretically, work performance is linked to job engagement, and to some extent, work satisfaction is a mixture of many attributes. Instead, overall work satisfaction is calculated as the sum of assessments of the job's different components (Macey & Schneider 2008). The five most frequently utilized components are job content, chances for development, supervision, compensation, and co-workers (Aziri 2011).

According to Lind & van den Bos (2002), individuals in uncertain environments want "fair" treatment from authorities. Therefore, an authority figure's perceived fairness would be relatively insignificant in stable circumstances or certainty but essential in uncertain situations. People feel worried about their future in unknown cases and want protection. Therefore, researchers have suggested that creating a positive atmosphere of cooperation, where people believe they have been treated fairly, is essential for guiding any challenging organizational transformation (Contreras & Gonzalez 2021).

H3. CCM is positively related to OCB.

Crises effect significantly impacts management teams' ability to make tough decisions (Tindale & Winget 2020). Team decisions are susceptible to the crisis impact. This is because concerns transform regular group functioning and thus make conventional treatments useless (Marks et al. 2001). Emerging and quickly changing information is associated with crises. In such circumstances, a typical strategy is to wait until all relevant information is available and make an educated choice. However, when options must be taken quickly in a crisis, such an approach is not feasible. For example, the pandemic resulted in significant changes in tourism; temporary airlines and hotels were closed, as were restaurants and rent-a-cars. These occurrences are impossible to recognize or even anticipate. Therefore, relevant information and data come from many sources and occur throughout time as crises unfold. When conflicting decisions include clear options between the collective and individual, they must practice self-control to choose to help the group (Martinsson et al. 2012).

H4. CCM is positively related to CC.

COVID-19 Concern

COVID-19 has spread quickly across the globe, causing significant medical and economic problems that affect people's everyday lives. Impacts on mental health may be discovered thru different avenues, such as disease outbreaks, depression, and economic recession. According to Brooks et al. (2020), the pandemic has caused mental health issues. Based on research, COVID-19 is associated with more depressive, anxiety, and post-traumatic stress symptoms and a potential increase in sleep. Similarly, Ammerman et al. (2021) highlighted a rise in online mental-health-related issues and a connection between social isolation and the past months' suicidal thoughts and suicide attempts. In order to prevent the COVID-19 from spreading, several countries have shut down *non-essential* economic sectors that affect the international economy, creating an enormous disturbance (WTO 2020). Based on statistics presented by the Associated Press (2020, April 9), between January 2, 2020, and March 23, 2020, the S&P 500 fell 31.32 percent. From March 27, 2020, to April 3, 2020, 6,648,000 Americans filed for unemployment, the highest in U.S. history.

Economic recessions also correlate with a significant deterioration in mental health (Alhenaidi & Huijt 2020). For example, the Great Crisis of 2008 in the United States was strongly associated with anxiety, depression, and drug use for about three to four years after the recession ended (Forbes & Krueger 2019). In addition, researchers have studied the effects of social exclusion, social isolation, and loneliness caused by health issues. Consequently, the population can suffer increased sadness, anxiety, stress, psychological load, anxiety, disturbed sleep, and elderly suicide, perhaps due to increasing loneliness and separation (Brooks et al. 2020). According to Southwick & Southwick (2020), loneliness, social isolation, and living alone are positively associated with increased mortality risk. There are external threats to societal health, such as the impact COVID-19 is having on mental health, financial worry, and adherence to self-quarantine recommendations. Therefore, it is necessary to evaluate COVID-19's impact on the labor population.

H5. COC is positively related to OCB.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior

OCB refers to a group of behaviors that people accept and put into practice without being formally compensated. When an employee assists coworkers in a stable workplace operation, they demonstrate altruism. OCB is an individual's discretionary activity that constructively supports an organization (Organ & Ryan 1995). Scholars have given a lot of attention to OCB (Chiang & Hsieh 2012). According to Organ (1990), OCBs are a class of pro-organizational behaviors that can neither be enforced on based on formal role obligations nor elicited by contractual guarantees of recompense. Employee OCBs are essential to organization performance since managers cannot predict all opportunities for employees' contributions, supervise all employees' behavior, or push employees into "going the extra mile" for the organization (p. 912). Employees' conscientiousness is demonstrated by their compliance with administrative regulations even when they are not being observed. In addition, the level of tolerance for an employee's discomfort demonstrates sportsmanship (Organ et al. 2006).

OCB differs from task performance or in-role behavior; it is more discretionary. Therefore, OCB cannot directly be associated with rewards to stimulate and promote a positive organizational climate in social psychology (Organ et al. 2006). Generally, researchers have concentrated on how OCB benefits both employees and organizations. For example, employees respond efficiently to the call of duty by assisting and mentoring coworkers, becoming involved and staying informed about the organization, speaking up and encouraging others, volunteering to take on additional responsibilities, and so on, and their supervisors reward them for doing so (Whiting et al. 2008). Similarly, when OCB is prevalent in the workplace, the organization becomes a more appealing workplace. Organizations benefit from OCB because it contributes to the development of social capital and *lubricates* the organization's social machinery, allowing it to function more effectively (Bolino et al. 2012). Aligned with those thoughts,

empirical researchers have found that OCB relates to team and organizational effectiveness indicators, including business performance, economic output, product quality, and customer support ratings (Podsakoff et al. 2009).

Therefore, OCB is mainly determined by psychological factors rather than an employee's knowledge, skills, and talents (Hoffman et al. 2007). Given that citizenship calls into question the foundations and functioning of fundamental institutions such as the market, the state, and civil society (Bendek 2002), OCBs have developed into a central moral tenet incorporated into some codes of ethical principles (Grit 2004). OCBs are intrinsically moral in how the individual chooses to engage in behaviors that benefit others (Peloza & Hassay 2006). Due to their critical role in promoting organizational effectiveness, efficiency, and success, OCBs have been intensively explored in ethical areas (Podsakoff et al. 2009).

Individual citizenship inside the firm—in which actions are referred to as "organizational citizenship behaviors" (OCBs)—is also considered critical for the company's longevity. According to some research, OCBs are consistently associated with organizational success (Organ et al. 2006). Workers may do OCBs in various ways, including partnering with others, orienting new employees, volunteering for additional work, and assisting others in their jobs. However, Lievens and Anseel (2004) stated that OCB should be examined in contexts other than the United States because the dimensionality of an OCB indicator may alter for different cultures.

H6. OCB is positively related to CC.

Corporate Citizenship

Corporate citizenship has gained greater acceptance in the global community as a group of business practices that positively impact societies and business entities (Maignan & Ferrell 2000). CC was launched as a performance-based re-conceptualization of corporate social responsibility (Matten et al. 2003) and was characterized as the corporation's role in administering citizens' rights. CC is a kind of self-regulation incorporated into a company model (Lam 2009). It is described as an organization's participation in activities that seem to advance a social objective beyond what is required by law (Camacho & Salazar-Concha 2020).

Carroll (1998) defined CC as having four dimensions or faces: first, an economic face, in which a good corporate citizen is expected to be profitable; second, a legal face, in which a good corporate citizen is expected to follow the law; third, ethical faces, in which an excellent corporate citizen engages in ethical behavior; and fourth, philanthropic face, in which an ideal corporate citizen gives back. Maignan et al. (1999) defined how enterprises fulfill their stakeholders' economic, legal, ethical, and discretionary duties.

According to Maignan & Ferrell (2003), CC encompasses various actions, including financial support for staff education, promoting ethical programs, adopting environmentally sustainable practices, and sponsorship of community activities. Gardberg & Fombrun (2006) propose that citizenship programs are strategic investments on par with research, development, and advertising. Maignan et al. (1999) demonstrated that market-oriented and humanistic environments promote proactive CC. Furthermore, CC has shown positive benefits for businesses in marketing strategy, including differentiation strategies to increase sales profits (Siegel & Vitaliano 2007), connecting social contribution to product sales, consumer, or investor reactions to CC (Maignan & Ferrell 2004).

Nevertheless, there is a shortage of information concerning CC from an individual standpoint. The last issue is how being a good corporate citizen affects workers' citizenship inside or outside the firm. Given the critical role that workers play in creating and executing organizational policies and practices, it is helpful to research the intersection between CC and OCB, particularly in these times of pandemics.

Undoubtedly, CC is not a call for businesses to shoulder the whole world's weight (Jeurissen 2004); it is distributed socially among companies that pretend to be citizens and take part in the obligation to pursue a social agenda beyond what is required by law. However, the debate remains if CC is advantageous to

their workers' internal citizenship. Many types of research have been conducted to determine the antecedents of CC or OCB. Nevertheless, just a few studies have been conducted on the link between perceived CC and the OCB done by individual workers, much alone on whether perceived CC is always beneficial for increasing their OCBs.

A firm's excellent CC examples will positively affect people's citizenship behavior toward the business. Although most of the research has examined numerous determinants of OCBs from three primary perspectives: individual characteristics, job characteristics, and inter-organizational characteristics, there is a shortage of understanding regarding how OCBs may influence perceived CC positively or negatively.

Methodology

Sample and Procedure

This study is based on a survey conducted by administering a questionnaire to business owners in the Santander Province in Colombia. A non-probabilistic convenience sampling was used. The sample was selected using the list of companies associated with the Chamber of Commerce of Bucaramanga. Initially, 200 entrepreneurs were identified and contacted, but only 105 agreed to the interview.

CC theory is the foundation for this study (Carroll 1998). The model supports socially conscious conduct and focuses on how companies relate to stakeholders and the environment by bringing attention to the disparity between business and society. According to the theory, corporations are to be economically responsible and should be able to cover their expenses, obey the law across the board, and adhere to ethical and high moral standards, including avoiding irresponsible behavior such as environmental degradation or selling unsafe products.

To facilitate interviews and follow the health protocol established by the government of Colombia due to the pandemic, telephone interviews were conducted from January to March 2021. Different industries were represented among the participating companies (retail, furniture, restaurants, agro-industrial, service, transportation, etc.). All companies declared an annual income of 25 thousand dollars or above. A five-point Likert scale was used for all items and constructs.

Measures

The Corona Virus Anxiety Scale (CAS) is a five-item scale with high reliability ($\alpha=.93$) and validity, as shown by a survey of 775 individuals; findings validate the CAS as a viable and valuable instrument (Lee 2020). COC was measured based on Nelson et al. (2020) scale. The authors found that individual differences in mental health symptoms in confirmed cases were significantly positively associated with increased COC. Aiken's V coefficient and 95% confidence intervals (95% CI) were used to quantify the degree of relevance, representativeness, and clarity. $V \geq .70$ with $95\% CI \geq .59$ indicates a positive assessment reagent. CCM scale was developed and tested, a nine-item scale with high reliability ($\alpha=.86$) and $AVE=.91$.

Company owners' OCB was determined using the Lee & Allen (2002) scale. The scale consists of sixteen items. The scale created by Maignan & Ferrell (2000) was used to gather data on CC. It is an 18-item measure. All scales statements were denoted by a standard five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5. SEM was used to carry out the analysis. SEM's multivariate statistical procedures allow checking functional, predictive, and causal hypotheses to test structural models. Consequently, the technique used within SEM for this research is Partial Least Squares (PLS). The model was tested using SmartPLS3 version 3.3.3 software.

Results

Figure 1 provides summary of the PLS results.

Figure 1: Summary of PLS Results

Source: authors

Different authors indicate that the Partial Least Squares (PLS) model results can be evaluated globally (general model) and locally (measurement model and structural model) (Henseler et al. 2016). The model fit test is considered the initial test in the evaluation with PLS (Camacho et al. 2020); then, the measurement and structural model evaluation must be carried out (Albort-Morant et al. 2018). According to Henseler et al. (2016), when using PLS-SEM, the model fit evaluation can be performed through the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) measurement, the Unweighted Squares Discrepancy (d_{ULS}) measurement, and the Geodesic Discrepancy (d_G) measurement. An SRMR value=0 indicates a perfect fit, and less than .05 is acceptable. Therefore, Henseler et al. (2016) consider a cutoff value of .08 is suitable for PLS route models. Table 1 presents all measurements' results below HI99; therefore, the required condition is met (Albort-Morant et al. 2018).

Table 1. Global Research Model Evaluation

	Estimated Model	HI95	HI99
SRMR	.08	.08	.09
d_{ULS}	4.56	3.92	4.90
d_G	2.61	3.15	3.68

Notes: HI95: bootstrap based on 95% percentiles; HI99 on 99% percentiles with 5000 subsamples.

We examined the internal consistency, convergent validity, and discriminant to evaluate the reflective measurement model following the steps recommended by the literature (Hair et al. 2017). Cross-factor

loadings analysis (Hair et al. 2014) evaluated each item's reliability. All cross-factorial loads of the variables met the conditions. Construct consistency was evaluated using the composite reliability (CR) and Cronbach's α , which must be greater than .7 (Hair et al. 2014). Table 2 shows that the set of constructs and dimensions satisfy all requirements ($\alpha > .81$, $CR > .91$, $AVE > .60$, $HTMT < 1$). The Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio of Correlations (HTMT) is a discriminant validity, meaning two latent variables that represent different theoretical concepts are statistically different. If the HTMT is smaller than one, discriminant validity can be established.

Table 2. Measurement Model Indicators Summary

Variables	Internal consistency		Convergent validity	Discriminant validity
	$\alpha > .7$	$CR > .7$	$AVE > .5$	$HTMT < 1$
COVID-19 Anxiety (CA)	.91	.94	.84	Yes
Confidence Crisis Management (CCM)	.86	.91	.77	Yes
Corporate Citizenship (CC)	.96	.96	.60	Yes
Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)	.94	.95	.65	Yes
COVID-19 Concern (COC)	.82	.92	.85	Yes

Structural Model Evaluation

We have followed the steps recommended by the literature to evaluate the structural model results (Hair et al. 2017). Table 3 exhibits values of Q^2 obtained using the blindfolding procedure for an omission distance=6. Concerning the values of Q^2 , it is possible to observe that the values are above 0 and have a positive sign. OCB and CC are assessed as medium predictive values and COC as low. These results provide evidence of the predictive relevance of the research model in terms of its endogenous variables. In Table 3, a medium effect in the CC construct with CCM is shown. The size effect was assessed using Cohen's f^2 (Cohen 1988). This measure assesses the change in R^2 when a particular exogenous construct is omitted from the model and if it has a substantive impact on endogenous constructs.

Table 3. Structural Model Coefficient Path Summary

Direct effects on endogenous constructs	Coefficients Path (β)	p Values	BCCI of 95%	f^2	q^2
COVID-19 Concern					
CA $\rightarrow$ COC	.36	.00	[-.20, -.51]	.15	.09
$R^2 = .12$					
$Q^2 = .08$					
Organizational Citizenship Behavior					
CA $\rightarrow$ OCB	-.26	.01	[-.42, -.07]	.08	.04
COC $\rightarrow$ OCB	.44	.00	[.26, .61]	.22	.12
CCM $\rightarrow$ OCB	.39	.00	[.25, .54]	.20	.10
$R^2 = .26$					
$Q^2 = .15$					
Corporate Citizenship					
OCB $\rightarrow$ CC	.41	.00	[.23, .55]	.23	.092
CCM $\rightarrow$ CC	.32	.00	[.16, .48]	.14	.241
$R^2 = .35$					
$Q^2 = .19$					

Notes: BCCI: bias-corrected confidence intervals based on a one tail distribution Student $t_{(5000)}$, $t_{(.05, 4999)} = 1.64$, $t_{(.01, 4999)} = 2.33$, $t_{(.001, 4999)} = 3.09$

Hypothesis Validation

Table 4 shows that the model had moderate and low predictive relevance for five of its endogenous constructs and one negative. H1 and H2 posited that CA would positively affect COC and OCB. The results show a positive effect on COC and a negative impact on OCB; therefore, H1 was supported, and H2 was not supported. H3 and H4 refer to the potential effect of CCM on OCB and CC. The results for H3 and H4 were positive, and both hypotheses were supported. On the other hand, H5 expected that COC would positively affect OCB; the results show a positive direct effect; therefore, H5 was supported. H6 stated a direct effect of OCB on CC; the results show a positive direct effect; therefore, H6 was supported. To complement the results presented in Table 4, Figure 1 depicts the relationships, path coefficients, signs, R² value, and Q² value.

Table 4. Hypothesis Testing

	Path coefficients (β)	<i>p</i> Sig.	Hypotheses
CA → COC	.36	.00	H1. Accepted
CA → OCB	-.26	.01	H2. Not Accepted
CCM → OCB	.39	.00	H3. Accepted
CCM → CC	.18	.00	H4. Accepted
COC → OCB	.44	.00	H5. Accepted
OCB → CC	.41	.00	H6. Accepted

Conclusions

This research aimed to examine the effects of CA and COC on OCB and the impact of OCB on CC. The research also examined the direct effects of CCM on OCB and CC. This study is pioneering work that focuses on exploring how the virus has impacted employees' behavior in their work settings and its effects on corporate citizenship. Based on the findings, CA increases COC, indicating that an increase in workers' anxiety resulting from the virus makes them more concerned and negatively impacts productivity and employees' performance. However, the results show that CA does not directly affect OCB. These results should be significant for managers and decision-makers because when the organization has created a solid relationship with employees, external events would not change employees' engagement with the corporation. In addition, these outcomes align with Keim et al. (2014) that more research is necessary about employees' attitudes toward returning to work, mainly work attitudes and OCB. These results are essential in studying employee psychology and filling the literature gap addressing employees' psychological effects and attitudes during the COVID-19 epidemic. Also, these outcomes are significant in the study of OCB because citizenship refers to being present someplace and conveys both rights and obligations.

According to the hypotheses, the findings are consistent with the idea that COC affects OCB. Managers must know that eliminating COVID-19 psychological impacts among workers is essential. Brooks et al. (2020) have shown that there has been an increase in mental health problems because of the pandemic. Therefore, corporations must understand that citizenship behaviors are derived from covenants with their employees that establish expectations and stimulate behaviors in favor of the well-being of others. When people feel worried about their future in unknown circumstances, they demand protection and solutions to their problems. Such protection should be provided by an authority figure who is seen to be fair and has extraordinary communication skills.

The research showed that effective CCM methods were linked with greater levels of OCB. People's feelings about their work and how it impacts their well-being are the findings that back up the claim that job satisfaction is associated with people's emotions (Gebauer & Lowman 2009). Contemporary companies rely on individuals willing to make discretionary contributions that benefit colleagues, other

employees, and the company. Citizenship actions can benefit companies on many levels while also helping to keep them operating correctly. This study has provided preliminary insights into how the COVID-19 pandemic affects OCB and CC. The current crisis offers businesses a fantastic chance to become more involved in community-based activities and perhaps kickstart a new era of community-based growth.

It is necessary to appreciate the effect of CCM on CC. These findings are coherent with Contreras & Gonzalez's (2021) suggestions that creating a positive atmosphere of cooperation, where people believe they have been treated fairly, is essential for promoting organizational change. These behaviors may shape active engagement and involvement in the local environment, helping others, and respecting their rights. Furthermore, citizenship is founded on the concept of a collaborative relationship between citizens and their community regulated by responsibilities to the collective and by individual self-interest.

The path coefficients' results on the relationship of COC on OCB (.44) and OCB on CC (.41) are remarkable, and both connections are significant and positive. These results confirm what Swaen & Maignan (2003) stated related to the interconnection between OCB and CC. In simple words, OCB oversees employees' behaviors related to ethics, and CC oversees activities that promote good citizenship in society. Indeed, these findings support companies' being more conducive to creating and displaying a good CC position with high OCBs. When workers consider their company ethical, they are consistent with its value system. Corporations that practice social responsibility foster reciprocal relationships between employers and employees, motivating employees to reciprocate with favorable attitudes and behaviors toward the organization.

OCB is related to what organizational members do, whereas CC defines what organizations do in the community in which they operate. Then, CC is frequently the product of the efforts of a few people; therefore, people are also highly essential in its development. The beneficiaries of these two civic activities are very different. Corporate citizens conduct themselves in a way that helps the organization. According to Maignan & Ferrell (2003), the business is always the primary winner in this scenario, with the organizational stakeholders primarily benefiting from CC. CC acts in the best interests of the community.

Findings confirm what Camacho & Salazar-Concha (2020) stated that corporations might use CC as a marketing strategy to distinguish their goods from rivals or improve their financial success. Companies that are good corporate citizens may be rewarded, for example, with increased consumer support. They may also be fostered by a culture that promotes peace and friendliness. Businesses see CC as another duty that they owe to society and place their commitment to the community and their stakeholders in these terms. While OCB and OC may be used for other reasons, such as impression management, they may be used alone.

Implications for Management

The study and its results have significant implications for how businesses should behave themselves. Companies need to project an image of a corporate citizen to society at large and their workers. When employees perceive their organizations to be good corporate citizens, they strive to become good citizens, thereby expending more discretionary effort toward accomplishing organizational goals. The study's results apply to any company interested in influencing employee behavior. To take advantage of this connection, a company must communicate its corporate citizenship activities to its workers. This study offers managers and practitioners important information, especially those in emerging markets and developing countries, on how necessary it is to eliminate the psychological impacts of COVID-19 among workers to improve the OCBs and exhibit a better CC position in front of the company's stakeholders. Finally, creating an environment that stimulates OCB among employees could be beneficial for corporations, more when a non-controllable crisis arises; the outcomes of this study show employees' positive attitudes toward OCB, even in times of COVID-19, and subsequently, due to the effect of OCB on CC, the opportunities of improving the citizen positioning on the society. Therefore, corporate strategies

and programs to improve OCB and CC among employees are essential in order to keep the workforce bonded to corporations' need.

Constraints and Further Research

The scope of this research is limited to Colombia, a developing nation. One limitation of the study is that the results are based on a small sample of businesses operating in a single Colombian area, which may not be generalizable. As a result, it is essential to research a developed country. A research framework may be designed to investigate the connection between COVID-19, OCB, and CC and evaluate the worldwide economic effect of the COVID-19 pandemic. Another constraint is the limited number of businesses involved in this study. In the future, a broad range of industries should be examined to further our knowledge of these phenomena across sectors and nations.

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